

The Role of Haptic Stimuli on Affective Reading: a Pilot Study

Shadi Ghiasi*, Getano Valenza, Maria Sole Morelli,
Matteo Bianchi, Enzo Pasquale Scilingo, and Alberto Greco

Abstract—The affective role of touch has opened new perspectives in human-machine interaction. This paper presents an emotion recognition algorithm to investigate the role of tactile stimuli conveyed through a wearable haptic system during affective reading. To this end, a group of 32 healthy volunteers underwent an emotional stimulation by reading affective texts, with and without the concurrent presence of pleasant haptic stimuli. Throughout the experiment, autonomic nervous system dynamics was quantified through heart rate variability (HRV) and electrodermal activity (EDA) analyses. EDA and HRV features were then used as input of a SVM-RFE learning algorithm for an automatic recognition of neutral and arousing texts. The affective recognition of the reading was performed in the presence or absence of the haptic stimulation. Results show that the affective perception induced by the neutral and arousing reading were discriminated with a significantly improved accuracy (+14.5%) when a caress-like haptic stimulus was conveyed to the user.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the frame of affective computing, many studies have been focused on the development of computational tools for the automatic identification of the emotional/mood state [1]. These affective detection systems may employ information from, e.g., speech activity, physiological signals, face expression, and behavioral patterns [1].

First challenge of affective studies lies in the emotional elicitation phase, because of the complex interactions between cognitive and neurophysiological responses. To this end, emotional images [2], sounds [3], movies and video clips [4], virtual reality settings [5], as well as affective reading [6] have been employed.

Indeed, a combination of the aforementioned stimuli comprising different elicitation modalities may improve the emotional experience and provide a more ecological scenario. This approach has been proposed to merge emotional musical excerpts and visual stimuli [7], or to combine affective audio, visual and haptic stimuli [8]. Particularly, the tactile stimulation may effectively enhance the emotional perception of the user [9]. The role of affective touch is due to specific tactile receptors, located in the skin, namely the slow conducting unmyelinated CT fibers [10], whose activity is strongly connected, at central nervous system level, to the contralateral primary and bilateral secondary somatosensory area, as well as to the contralateral middle and posterior insula cortex [10], which are brain regions directly involved in the emotion regulation processes. Moreover, previous studies have highlighted that CT-mediated emotional perception is

correlated with the physical characteristics of tactile stimuli such as velocity, force, contact and material [11]–[13]. In this context, wearable systems for haptic stimulation have been designed for social interaction or assistive technology scenarios [14], [15]. In Bianchi et al. [16], we have proved that haptic devices designed to deliver kinaesthetic and/or cutaneous discriminative cues can also convey affective inputs to the brain.

In this study, we aim to investigate the role of affective haptic stimuli in subjects reading affective texts, with the hypothesis that affective touch may enhance the emotional perception. To this aim, haptic stimuli were conveyed through a recently developed wearable device [17], and a pattern recognition system was employed to automatically discern between neutral and arousing stimuli, in combination or not with haptic stimulation.

With the subjects' self-assessment constituting a ground-truth reference, the emotional state of 32 subjects has been inferred using autonomic nervous system (ANS) signals, whose dynamics is deemed to be an effective emotional marker [18]. More specifically, we have extracted features from heart rate variability (HRV) and the electrodermal activity (EDA) [19], because of their efficacy highlighted in recent emotion recognition studies involving affective haptic stimulation [12], [20].

Methodological details, as well as Results and Conclusion follow below.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Subjects Recruitment, Experimental protocol and Acquisition set-up

Thirty-two undergraduates students (16 females) from the University of Pisa participated to this study giving their written informed consent. The study was approved by Ethical Committee of the University of Pisa. The subjects were asked to read aloud two types of texts. The texts were chosen with the aim of eliciting the reader with two different levels of arousal (intensity of perception) and valence (pleasantness/unpleasantness) according to the definition of the Circumplex model of affect (CMA) [21].

Four texts were employed: two with high arousal, negative valence contents while the other two neutral. We asked the subjects to rank each text in terms of arousal and valence using the standard Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) [22] to ensure the elicitation was powerful to induce physiological responses.

During the affective text elicitation, the subjects might have been exposed to haptic elicitation through a wearable haptic device conveying a caress-like stimuli (see more

Authors are with the Department of Information Engineering and Research Center "E. Piaggio", Faculty of Engineering, University of Pisa, Via G. Caruso 16 - 56122, Pisa, Italy.

* Corresponding author email: shadi.ghiasi@centropiaggio.unipi.it

Fig. 1. The CUFF device on the arm of a subject. The inside of the belt was covered in silk

details in the next section). The timeline of the experiment included four sessions that were performed by subjects randomly. The four sessions were as follows:

- High arousal, negative valence text reading (A).
- Neutral text reading (N).
- High arousal, negative valence text reading accompanied by haptic caress (AC).
- Neutral text reading accompanied by haptic caress (NC).

Each session was preceded by 40s of resting and followed by 1 minute of recovery. The Biopac system mp35 device was used to record both the ECG and EDA signals.

B. The haptic feedback wearable device

The tactile stimulation was conveyed through a wearable haptic CUFF (clenching upper-limb force feedback wearable device), which is able to transfer both the normal and tangential force cues [17]. The physical characteristics are the weight of 230g with overall dimensions $12.4 \times 7.0 \times 5.8$ cm (see Figure 1). The device is equipped with two motors independently controlled that are able to stretch a layer of fabric. More detailed information can be found in [17]. The fabric strip can be made of different material and, in this experiment, we used silk [23] to induce a positive valence of the tactile elicitation. Moreover, in previous studies, it has been proven that the emotional perception of tactile stimulus changes according to contact force and velocity [12], [16]. Specifically, a velocity of 3 cm/s and a force as low as 2N convey pleasant and relaxation perception to the subject. Accordingly, the CUFF was set and controlled to convey these values.

C. Statistical analysis of the SAM scores

To test the different perception of arousal and valence elicited by the experimental sessions, we performed a statistical analysis of the scores given by subjects using the SAM test. The valence values were ranged between -2 (most unpleasant) to 2 (most pleasant) and arousal between 1 (lowest arousal) to 5 (highest arousal). Specifically, we statistically compared the scores corresponding to the N and A sessions and those corresponding to the NC and AC sessions. The p-values were obtained by applying the Wilcoxon non-parametric tests for paired data, with null hypothesis of equal medians between samples.

TABLE I
LIST OF EXTRACTED FEATURES

Feature list	Description
HRV (Time domain)	
Mean (RR) [ms]	Mean of RR intervals
Std (RR) [ms]	Standard deviation of RR intervals
RMSSD [ms]	Root mean Square of successive RRs
PNN50 %	Percentage of successive RRs
HRV (Frequency domain)	
LF [ms ²]	Absolute LF power
HF [ms ²]	Absolute HF power
LF/HF	LF/HF power ratio
HRV (Nonlinear)	
SampEN	Sample entropy
EDA (Phasic component)	
MaxPeak [μS]	Maximum amplitude of phasic
SumPeak [μS]	Sum of amplitudes of phasic peaks
MeanPhasic [μS]	Mean value of phasic signal
StdPhasic [μS]	Standard deviation of phasic signal
EDA (Tonic component)	
MeanTonic [μS]	Mean tonic activity
StdTonic [μS]	Standard deviation of tonic activity
MaxTonic [μS]	Maximum amplitude of tonic activity

D. Autonomic nervous system quantification

ECG and EDA were processed to quantify the autonomic nervous system activity.

The heart rate variability (HRV) time series was extracted from the ECG signal by detecting the R peaks through the well known Pan-Tompkins algorithm [24]. Conventional features in the time, frequency and nonlinear domains were extracted from the HRV signal using the Kubious software. Table I shows the description of the extracted features.

EDA measures the variation in the skin conductance (SC) induced by the sudomotor nerve activity (SMNA), which modulates the sweat section of the eccrine glands. Therefore, it is considered an ideal way to monitor the activity of sympathetic nervous system [25]. The EDA signal is composed of two main components, namely the tonic and phasic signals, that differ in time scale and relationship with the triggering stimuli. The tonic signal is the slow-varying component that represents the overall psycho-physiological state of a subject. The phasic component represents the rapid variations in the EDA signal that are directly evoked by an external stimulus [26]. Phasic and tonic rely on different neural mechanisms and, consequently, both convey relevant and non-redundant information about the ANS activity.

In this study, we applied a decomposition algorithm called cvxEDA [27], whereby we can decompose the EDA signal into the tonic and phasic components. Whereupon, the phasic and tonic activities were quantified by extracting a set of features as described in Table I.

E. Classification algorithm

We considered two recognition tasks, i.e., we classified the neutral and arousing texts in the absence (N vs A) or presence (NC vs AC) of the simultaneous haptic stimulation conveyed by the CUFF.

The classification was done by implementing the nonlinear Support Vector Machine (SVM) integrated with a wrapper feature selection method, i.e., the recursive feature elimination (RFE) as proposed in [28]. This SVM-RFE algorithm

has been proven to be a reliable classification and feature selection method also in case of a dataset of highly correlated features.

To validate the classification procedure and estimate the recognition accuracy, we used the Leave-One-Subject-Out (LOSO) cross-validation. Assuming as input to the classifier data from N subjects, at each iteration of the LOSO the model is trained on N-1 subject samples and tested on the excluded one. The whole procedure is repeated N times and the feature ranking and classification accuracy is achieved by computing the median ranking over all folds.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present results of the statistical analysis performed on SAM scores, as well as the performances achieved by the two recognition systems, i.e., N vs A and NC vs AC.

Statistics on self-assessed scores along the arousal and valence dimensions demonstrates that the A and AC texts were significantly more arousing and unpleasant than the N and NC texts, respectively (Table II).

TABLE II

SAM MEDIAN \pm MEDIAN ABSOLUTE DEVIATION (MAD) SCORES AND STATISTICS RESULTS FOR THE A vs N AND AC vs NC COMPARISONS

	A	N	p-value	AC	NC	p-value
Valence	$-1 \pm .5$	0 ± 0	$8 \cdot 10^{-7}$	-1 ± 1	0 ± 0	$7 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Arousal	3 ± 1	1 ± 0	$9 \cdot 10^{-7}$	3 ± 1	1 ± 0	$6 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Concerning the classification analyses, the maximum accuracies achieved by the SVM-RFE learning algorithm in discriminating N vs A and NC vs AC are reported in terms of confusion matrices in Table III and IV. While the proposed recognition system was not able to satisfactorily distinguish between N and A sessions (accuracy of 54.84%), the recognition accuracy achieved considering the data gathered during a haptic elicitation (NC vs AC) significantly improved up to 69.35%.

Figures 2 and 3 show the accuracy trend at each iteration of the RFE procedure for both recognition tasks. The maximum accuracies were achieved considering only the first two (N vs A) or three (NC vs AC) features. Both feature rankings are listed in Table V. It is worthwhile noting that the two rankings and consequently the subsets of features achieving the maximum accuracy were different.

IV. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated the role of affective haptic stimulation on emotional reading. Thirty-two subjects were asked to read texts having different emotional value, i.e., neutral texts vs high-arousal negative texts. This has

TABLE III

CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE (N vs E) RECOGNITION TASK.

Final feature-set	N	A
N	51.61 %	48.39 %
A	41.94 %	58.06 %
Recognition accuracy: 54.84 %		

TABLE IV

CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE (NC vs AC) RECOGNITION TASKS.

Final feature-set	NC	AC
NC	61.29 %	38.71 %
AC	22.58 %	77.42 %
Recognition accuracy: 69.35 %		

Fig. 2. Validation set accuracy for the classification of N vs A phases as a function of feature rankings according to the SVM-RFE LOSO algorithm.

been confirmed by the statistical analyses performed on the subjects' self-assessment scores. The experimental task was repeated twice, where one repetition included also the affective haptic stimulation.

We characterized ANS dynamics through features derived from EDA and HRV series. Particularly, several features were extracted to build two datasets comprising a combination of HRV and EDA features in the presence or absence of the haptic stimulation, respectively. Aiming to obtain powerful processing of the EDA signal, we applied the recently proposed cvxEDA model to decompose the observed SC signal into its tonic and phasic components.

Classification results demonstrate that the SVM-RFE was not able to satisfactorily distinguish between the neutral and arousing session (54.84%), whereas its performance significantly improved in the presence of the haptic elicitation, i.e., NC vs AC (69.35%).

The poor accuracy in the N vs A classification is not surprising. In fact, it is known that recognizing emotional

Fig. 3. Validation set accuracy for the classification of NC vs AC phases as a function of feature rankings according to the SVM-RFE-LOSO algorithm.

TABLE V

RANKING OF THE FIRST SEVEN FEATURES PERFORMED BY RFE ALGORITHM FOR BOTH RECOGNITION TASKS

	N vs A	NC vs AC
1	HF [$m.s^2$] *	LF/HF*
2	SumPeak [μS]*	SampEN*
3	LF [$m.s^2$]	MaxPeak [μS]*
4	StdPhasic [μS]	StdTonic [μS]
5	RMSSD [$m.s$]	MaxTonic [μS]
6	Std(RR) [$m.s$]	MeanTonic [μS]
7	Mean(RR) [$m.s$]	LF [$m.s^2$]

states during speaking activity through only monitoring the ANS signals is a challenging task due to the confounding interaction of the speech itself in ANS dynamics [25], [29]. In addition, the reading-out-loud introduces a stressful effect that can not be underestimated. Our results also highlight a significant increase in recognition accuracy of emotional stimuli (+14.5%) when a haptic device is used. At a speculation level, the presence of a positive haptic stimulus might induce a relaxation effect [12], which leads to a stronger affective perception and, consequently, to an easier discrimination despite the speech activity.

Selected feature-set leading to higher accuracy in the NC vs AC recognition comprised three features only, which are related to both sympathetic and parasympathetic activities, as well as their interaction. Moreover, the small number of features (i.e., dimensions) is a further indicator of robustness and generalization ability of the devised classification algorithm.

Although preliminary, the outcomes of this study corroborate the widely-recognized affective role of touch, suggesting a new haptic-based stimulation paradigm to enhance users' emotional experience. To this aim, the combination with other sensory modalities (e.g. acoustic, olfactory) will be also considered and investigated in the future. These results open fascinating perspectives in the field of advanced human-machine interaction and human-human communication through wearables. In literature there are several examples of mechatronic systems that deliver haptic stimuli to elicit emotional responses in users. Other studies will also aim at performing a detailed analysis of the texts (linguistic structure and sentiment analysis) to explore possible correlations between linguistic and ANS features, aiming at improving the emotional recognition accuracy. Finally, we will extend the research to patients with pathological and mental disorders to investigate whether the haptic stimuli can enrich emotion recognition also in this population.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. D. Mello, A. Kappas, and J. Gratch, "The affective computing approach to affect measurement," *Emotion Review*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 174–183, 2018.
- [2] P. J. Lang, "International affective picture system (iaps): Digitized photographs, instruction manual and affective ratings," *Technical report*, 2005.
- [3] Y.-P. Lin, C.-H. Wang, T.-P. Jung, T.-L. Wu, S.-K. Jeng, J.-R. Duann, and J.-H. Chen, "Eeg-based emotion recognition in music listening," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 57, no. 7, pp. 1798–1806, 2010.
- [4] S. Koelstra, C. Muhl, M. Soleymani, J.-S. Lee, A. Yazdani, T. Ebrahimi, T. Pun, A. Nijholt, and I. Patras, "Deap: A database for emotion analysis; using physiological signals," *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 18–31, 2012.
- [5] E. Leon, G. Clarke, V. Callaghan, and F. Sepulveda, "A user-independent real-time emotion recognition system for software agents in domestic environments," *Engineering applications of artificial intelligence*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 337–345, 2007.
- [6] R. A. Calvo and S. Mac Kim, "Emotions in text: dimensional and categorical models," *Computational Intelligence*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 527–543, 2013.
- [7] T. Baumgartner, M. Esslen, and L. Jäncke, "From emotion perception to emotion experience: Emotions evoked by pictures and classical music," *International journal of psychophysiology*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 34–43, 2006.
- [8] J. Mladenović, "Considering gut biofeedback for emotion regulation," in *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM International Joint Conference and 2018 International Symposium on Pervasive and Ubiquitous Computing and Wearable Computers*. ACM, 2018, pp. 942–945.
- [9] M. J. Hertenstein, "Touch: Its communicative functions in infancy," *Human Development*, vol. 45, no. 2, pp. 70–94, 2002.
- [10] E. T. Rolls, "The affective and cognitive processing of touch, oral texture, and temperature in the brain," *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 237–245, 2010.
- [11] G. Valenza, A. Greco, M. Bianchi, M. Nardelli, S. Rossi, and E. P. Scilingo, "Eeg oscillations during caress-like affective haptic elicitation," *Psychophysiology*, p. e13199, 2018.
- [12] A. Greco, G. Valenza, M. Nardelli, M. Bianchi, L. Citi, and E. P. Scilingo, "Force-velocity assessment of caress-like stimuli through the electrodermal activity processing: Advantages of a convex optimization approach," *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 91–100, 2017.
- [13] A. Klöcker, M. Wiertlewski, V. Théate, V. Hayward, and J.-L. Thonnard, "Physical factors influencing pleasant touch during tactile exploration," *Plos one*, vol. 8, no. 11, p. e79085, 2013.
- [14] S. Fani, S. Ciotti, M. G. Catalano, G. Grioli, A. Tognetti, G. Valenza, A. Ajoudani, and M. Bianchi, "Simplifying telerobotics: Wearability and teleimpedance improves human-robot interactions in teleoperation," *IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 77–88, 2018.
- [15] T. L. Chen, C.-H. A. King, A. L. Thomaz, and C. C. Kemp, "An investigation of responses to robot-initiated touch in a nursing context," *International Journal of Social Robotics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 141–161, 2014.
- [16] M. Bianchi, G. Valenza, A. Lanata, A. Greco, M. Nardelli, A. Bicchi, and E. P. Scilingo, "On the role of affective properties in hedonic and discriminant haptic systems," *International Journal of Social Robotics*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 87–95, 2017.
- [17] S. Casini, M. Morvidoni, M. Bianchi, M. Catalano, G. Grioli, and A. Bicchi, "Design and realization of the cuff-clenching upper-limb force feedback wearable device for distributed mechano-tactile stimulation of normal and tangential skin forces," in *Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), 2015 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 1186–1193.
- [18] S. D. Kreibitz, "Autonomic nervous system activity in emotion: A review," *Biological psychology*, vol. 84, no. 3, pp. 394–421, 2010.
- [19] R. D. Lane, K. McRae, E. M. Reiman, K. Chen, G. L. Ahern, and J. F. Thayer, "Neural correlates of heart rate variability during emotion," *Neuroimage*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 213–222, 2009.
- [20] G. Valenza, A. Greco, L. Citi, M. Bianchi, R. Barbieri, and E. Scilingo, "Inhomogeneous point-processes to instantaneously assess affective haptic perception through heartbeat dynamics information," *Scientific reports*, vol. 6, p. 28567, 2016.
- [21] J. Posner, J. A. Russell, and B. S. Peterson, "The circumplex model of affect: An integrative approach to affective neuroscience, cognitive development, and psychopathology," *Development and psychopathology*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 715–734, 2005.
- [22] M. M. Bradley and P. J. Lang, "Measuring emotion: the self-assessment manikin and the semantic differential," *Journal of behavior therapy and experimental psychiatry*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 49–59, 1994.
- [23] A. Greco, A. Guidi, M. Bianchi, G. Valenza, E. P. Scilingo *et al.*, "Brain dynamics induced by pleasant/unpleasant tactile stimuli conveyed by different fabrics," *IEEE journal of biomedical and health informatics*, 2019.
- [24] J. Pan and W. J. Tompkins, "A real-time qrs detection algorithm," *IEEE Trans. Biomed. Eng.*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 230–236, 1985.
- [25] W. Boucsein, *Electrodermal activity*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2012.
- [26] M. Benedek and C. Kaernbach, "Decomposition of skin conductance data by means of nonnegative deconvolution," *Psychophysiology*, vol. 47, no. 4, pp. 647–658, 2010.
- [27] A. Greco, G. Valenza, A. Lanata, E. P. Scilingo, and L. Citi, "cvxeda: A convex optimization approach to electrodermal activity processing," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 63, no. 4, pp. 797–804, 2016.
- [28] K. Yan and D. Zhang, "Feature selection and analysis on correlated gas sensor data with recursive feature elimination," *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*, vol. 212, pp. 353–363, 2015.
- [29] B. Schuller, F. Friedmann, and F. Eyben, "Automatic recognition of physiological parameters in the human voice: Heart rate and skin conductance," in *Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP), 2013 IEEE International Conference on*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 7219–7223.